

Incidence of metabolic syndrome in polycystic ovarian syndrome in Iranian women

Somayeh Haghi Karamallah*, Somayeh Taei**, Elham Safavi[◇], Fatemeh Rajani* and Mahnaz Afraze^{△,1}

*MSc in Midwifery, Student Research Committee, Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, Shiraz, Iran., **Department of Biochemistry, Sharekord University, Sharekord, Iran., [◇]School of Medicine Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences, Ahvaz, Iran., [△]Department of Nursing and Midwifery, Islamic Azad University, Dezful branch, Dezful, Iran.

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is the most common cause of chronic anovulation, including 5-10% of women in reproductive ages. The association between increased insulin resistance and polycystic ovaries is now well-recognized. This clinical association of hyperinsulinemia and anovulatory hyperandrogenism is commonly found throughout the world. Insulin resistance is only one component of a condition which is now called metabolic syndrome. In different studies, the prevalence of this syndrome outbreak is reported at 7-43%. This study was performed to determine the prevalence and predictors of the metabolic syndrome in PCOS in the southwest of Iran.

Materials and Methods: The study included 62 women who were diagnosed with PCOS, according to the Rotterdam criteria. Metabolic syndrome was assessed according to the criteria of the American National Cholesterol Panel (ATP-III criteria). The prevalence of metabolic syndrome was studied through measuring the following items: fasting glucose, triglyceride, HDL cholesterol, blood pressure, weight, height and waist circumference. We considered the patients as a metabolic syndrome group who has 3 or more cases.

Results: Based on this research, the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in Ahwaz women was estimated 14.6%, the prevalence for individual components comprising the metabolic syndrome were: fasting glucose concentrations greater than or equals to 110 mg/dl in 11 patient(17.7%), hypertension in 9 patients (14.5%), BMI higher or equals to 30 in 14 patients (22.6%), waist circumference greater than or equals to 88 cm in 22 patients (35.5%), HDL less than 40 mg/dl in 10 patients (24%), triglyceride greater than or equals to 150 mg/dl in 8 patients (9.4%), IFG in 23 patients (37.1%), diabetes in 5 patients (8.07%) and dislipidemia in 32 patients(51.62%).

Conclusions: Our results show the metabolic syndrome and its elements frequently occur in women with PCOS, particularly those with the classic picture of the syndrome. The latter combination places them at risk for cardiovascular diseases and screening for those disturbances is required in patients with PCOS.

KEYWORDS BMI, HDL, IFG, PCOS, Metabolic syndrome

Introduction

Metabolic syndrome is an endocrine disturbance, including insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, obesity, and hypertension. It is associated with a two-fold increased risk of cardiovascular disease and a five-fold increased risk of type 2 diabetes [1,2] The National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel (NCEPATP III) guidelines define MBS as having three or more of the following abnormalities:

Copyright © 2019 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.Incidence-of-metabolic-syndrome-polycystic-ovarian
First Received: July 31, 2019
Accepted: August 10, 2019
Manuscript Associate Editor: Ivan Inkov (BG)

¹ Mahnaz Afraze[△] Department of Nursing and Midwifery, Islamic Azad University, Dezful branch, Dezful, Iran.; Email: ashrafalemi97@gmail.com

1. waist circumference in females greater than 88 cm,
2. fasting serum glucose at least 110mg/dl,
3. fasting serum triglycerides at least 150mg/dl,
4. serum high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) less than 50 mg/dl
5. blood pressure at least 130/85mmHg [3].

Some studies showed impaired glucose metabolism, raised blood pressure and dyslipidemia that currently affects approximately one in every five women of reproductive age[4,5]

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most common gynaecological endocrinopathy among reproductive-aged women [6,7]. The prevalence of PCOS has been reported from 2.2 to 26% in different studies conducted in various countries, depending on sampling method, the criteria used for its definition and the method used to define each criterion [5,8]. In a study by Tehrani et al., the prevalence of PCOS in a community sample of Iranian population was 7.1% using the National Institute of Health (NIH) definition, 11.7% by the Androgen Excess Society (AES) criteria and 14.6% using the Rotterdam consensus definition[8]. The pathogenesis of PCOS is not fully understood, although genetic, metabolic and neuroendocrine interactions, as well as environmental factors, were discussed elsewhere[9-11] [8-11]. Alterations in several metabolic pathways such as steroid hormone regulation and insulin signalling pathway abnormalities were discussed in the pathophysiology of PCOS[12, 13]. More than 50 percent of women with PCOS are obese or overweight, that may predispose them to metabolic disorders[14].

The prevalence of metabolic syndrome in polycystic ovary syndrome has been studied in different populations. Reported prevalence is 43% in the U.S., 28.4% in Brazil, 24.9% in Hong Kong Chinese women, and only 1.6% in Czech women[15-18]. These varied data indicate the need for evaluation of metabolic syndrome in different populations, as it would help in planning screening strategies to prevent long-term effects.

Hence, this study aimed to estimate the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in women with PCOS presenting in Iranian women.

Method

This is a retrospective study in patients with menstrual disorders and symptoms of hyperandrogenism who were referred to the Gynaecology clinic of Imam Ali, Andimeshk city, Iran. The PCOS diagnosis has been done through sonography approach and confirmed based on Rotterdam criteria 2013 also a measurement of hydroxyl progesterone, prolactin, FSH, LH, testosterone, overnight dexamethasone, T4 and TSH have been performed to exclude other etiological agents. The patients with confirmed PCOS and non-other etiological agents have been entered in the study. The various markers of metabolic syndrome, including serum levels of fasting blood sugar (Kimia Pajooan Inc., Tehran), triglycerides, HDL (High Density Lipoprotein), LDL, cholesterol and total cholesterol (Pars Inc., Tehran), blood pressure, weight, height and waist circumference also BMI have been evaluated and measured in all patients. Also, all the patients have been subjected to the questionnaire, such as age and symptoms of the polycystic ovarian disease (hirsutism, acne, hair loss, infertility, menstrual disorders). Based on the criteria ATP_III, abdominal obesity with waist circumference greater than 35 inches

(about cm 88), HDL cholesterol less than 50 mg/dl, Triglycerides greater than or equal to 150 mg/dl and hypertension equal or greater than 85/130 mmHg have been considered as the main criteria for diagnosis of the patients with metabolic syndrome.

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive statistics were demonstrated with mean, standard deviation and percent. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used for normal distribution values. The mean differences between groups were analyzed using Independent Samples t-test. To explore the correlation of quality and to assess the relationship of quantity values, Chi square test and Spearman rho was used, respectively. Chi square test was used for comparison of proportions.

Result

Between the years 2017 to 2018, fifty-three women have been diagnosed with PCOS. Based on the criteria, nine patients (14.6%) have been determined with metabolic syndrome. These patients have a higher weight, waist circumference, BMI, and fasting glucose than patients who do not have metabolic syndrome. However, patients with metabolic syndrome showed a lower average level of HDL compared to patients without metabolic syndrome. Furthermore, there is no significant difference in the average age, height, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, triglycerides, total cholesterol and LDL between patients with metabolic syndrome and other patients. The demographic information of the patients is shown in Table 1.

Prevalence of hypertension in patients with metabolic syndrome was 6/28 % and in patients who did not have metabolic syndrome was 4/4%, but this variation was not significant ($p>0.05$). The prevalence of dyslipidemia in patients with metabolic syndrome compared to other PCOS patients was significantly higher ($p>0.05$). The BMI higher than 30 was more frequent in patients with metabolic syndrome than other patients ($p<0.05$).

Prevalence of hypertension and diabetes or IFG in patients with PCOS who have a BMI greater than or equal to 25 was significantly higher than in patients with PCOS and BMI less than 25; there is no significant difference for dyslipidemia between these groups ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3).

Discussion

PCOS and metabolic syndrome are the two most common endocrine disorders in women, especially with industrial and urban lifestyle. The pathogenesis of PCOS is not fully understood, but as the endocrine disorder, there are some promising signs that have shown this disease can originate from metabolic pathway disturbances such as hyperinsulinemia and insulin resistance in lean and obese women, interestingly these two metabolic disturbances also can be found in metabolic syndrome (19,20). Based on the common features between PCOS and metabolic syndrome and the important role of insulin resistance in patients with PCOS, some studies have shown the higher prevalence of metabolic syndrome in PCOS patients in compared to general population however these findings are not supported in different ethnic groups which are mostly owing to various description of PCOS or metabolic syndrome, different cultural and environmental status and selection of control group [16-18]

Table 1 Demographic information of patients based on metabolic syndrome markers. $P \leq 0.05$ is considered as significant.

Variable	Patients without metabolic syndrome	Patients with metabolic syndrome	P-value
Age	25 ± 6.7	23.3 ± 3.2	0.34
Weight	62.5 ± 8.8	79.7 ± 9.21	< 001
Height	160.4 ± 3.0	163.9 ± 3.5	0.58
Waist circumference	86.3 ± 5.8	98.4 ± 7.9	< 001
BMI	24.2 ± 6.3	30.1 ± 5.2	< 001
Systolic blood pressure	10.8 ± 1.2	10.4 ± 0.8	0.78
Diastolic blood pressure	8.9 ± 0.4	7.23 ± 0.4	0.23
FBS	98 ± 12.4	110 ± 13.1	0.03
TG	89.5 ± 27.2	115 ± 34.9	0.17
TC	168.6 ± 25.2	176.2 ± 28.8	0.67
LDL	114.9 ± 14.2	117.3 ± 25.2	0.87
HDL	54.8 ± 10.3	40.3 ± 8.2	0.04

Table 2 Metabolic syndrome criteria in patients with PCOS.

Variable		Metabolic syndrome	
		Yes	No
Hypertension	Yes	3	4
	No	6	49
Dyslipidemia	Yes	8	24
	No	1	29
Diabetes and IGF	Yes	5	28
	No	4	35
BMI ≥ 30	Yes	5	9
	No	4	53

Table 3 Prevalence of individual characteristics of the metabolic syndrome stratified by body mass index in patients with PCOS.

Variable		Body Mass Index (BMI)	
		<25	≥25
Hypertension	<130/85	32	34
	≥130/85	1	6
Dyslipidemia	Yes	15	17
	No	13	17
Diabetes and IGF	Yes	13	20
	No	18	11

Based on the controversial findings of the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in PCOS patients, this study was designed to evaluate the prevalence and associated markers of metabolic syndrome in patients with PCOS in the southwest of Iran that has different environmental and cultural features in compared to another part of Iran. Previous studies in Iran had controversial findings of the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in PCOS patients [21-23]. Our results show higher weight, waist circumference, BMI, fasting glucose and lower HDL levels in 7 patients (13.5%) with PCOS. However, our results are in consistent with the prevalence rate of metabolic syndrome in PCOS patients in Italy [24] Bulgaria [25] China [26] and in contrast with United States [27] and Brazil [28]. This low rate of metabolic syndrome frequency in PCOS patients is consistent with Hosseinpanah et al. [21] who have shown the low frequency of this syndrome in PCOS in Iran. However, our result is lower than some other studies that have been conducted in the north of Iran; the rate of metabolic syndrome have been reported between 22% to 28% of PCOS patients [21,29,30,31]. The discrepancy in different parts of the world and different province of Iran can be related to the environmental and cultural factors that are completely different between the studies also diagnostic criteria, and sample size is other important factors. Therefore, the establishment of a comprehensive correlation between metabolic syndrome and PCOS requires a more and precise definition of each syndrome and determination of involved factors for both disorders.

Android obesity is associated with increased risk of cardiovascular disease and lower HDL, and PCOS patients are suffering from Android obesity pattern of Android [32]. In this study, 11.5% of patients were obese (BMI>30) also more weighting (BMI>25) were found in all patients. Also, waist circumference ≥ cm 88 was seen in 34.1% of patients. The patients with metabolic syndrome have a higher weight, waist circumference and BMI than others. These results supported the idea that obesity is a common finding in PCOS patients and can be an etiological agent to initiate or/and progress of PCOS.

Furthermore, according to this study, the prevalence of high blood pressure, diabetes or IFG in patients with PCOS who have a BMI higher than or equal to 25 are higher than in patients with PCOS who have a BMI less than 25. In this matched-BM, I comparison, the prevalence of dyslipidemia is not significantly different between the two groups. Lankarani et al. [22] also have shown any significant variation for dyslipidemia between obese and non-obese women. In contrast, Holte et al. [33] have indicated higher LDL and total cholesterol in obese PCOS patients compared to other patients. These differences can be related to the various genetic background, race and lifestyle. Obesity can induce high blood pressure, insulin resistance and IFG. Therefore weight loss should be advised in PCOS patients to reduce the risk of other metabolic disorders, also the possibility of PCOS progression as a metabolic disturbance.

In the current study, dyslipidemia is found in all of the patients, and the rate of dyslipidemia is higher in PCOS patients with metabolic syndrome compared to other PCOS patients. The HDL level is lower in PCOS patients with metabolic syndrome, but the TG level is not different between PCOS patients with metabolic syndrome and others. These findings are in contrast to the results of Ehrmann et al. [14] and Soares et al. [18], this discrepancy can be related to the low average age of our patients (24±6.8) that can affect the level of TG. Given the high prevalence of dyslipidemia in these patients and important role of dyslipidemia in cardiovascular disease, the evaluation of dyslipidemia should be considered in PCOS patients to reduce the cardiovascular risks in these patients.

Conclusions

Given the prevalence of metabolic syndrome in PCOS patients, the screening of metabolic syndrome in PCOS patients should be considered to find mild and moderate cases of metabolic syndrome to reduce the possibility of cardiovascular and other disorders in these patients.

Ethics committee approval

Ethical committee of Azad University of Dezfoul.

Competing Interests

The authors declared that this review was done independently without any conflict of interest of any organizations that would lead this review to bias.

References

1. Fronzo R, Ferrannini A. Multifaceted syndrome responsible for NIDDM, obesity, hypertension, dyslipidaemia and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. *Diabetes Care* 1991; 14:173.
2. Grundy SM, Cleeman JJ, Daniels SR, Donato KA, Eckel RH, Franklin BA, et al. Diagnosis and management of the metabolic syndrome: an American Heart Association/National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute scientific statement. *Circulation* 2005; 112(17):2735-2752.
3. Health NIo. Third Report of the National Cholesterol Education Program Expert Panel on detection, evaluation, and treatment of high blood cholesterol in adults (Adult Treatment Panel III). Executive Summary Bethesda, MD, National Institutes of Health, National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute (NIH publ no 01-3670) 2001.
4. Cornier M-A, Dabelea D, Hernandez TL, Lindstrom RC, Steig AJ, Stob NR, et al. The metabolic syndrome. *Endocrine reviews* 2008; 29(7):777-822.
5. Ford ES, Giles WH, Mokdad AH. Increasing prevalence of the metabolic syndrome among US adults. *Diabetes care* 2004; 27(10):2444-2449.
6. Kauffman RP, Baker TE, Baker VM, DiMarino P, Castracane VD. Endocrine and metabolic differences among phenotypic expressions of polycystic ovary syndrome according to the 2003 Rotterdam consensus criteria. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* 2008; 198(6):670. e671-670. e610.
7. Azziz R, Woods KS, Reyna R, Key TJ, Knochenhauer ES, Yildiz BO. The prevalence and features of the polycystic ovary syndrome in an unselected population. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism* 2004; 89(6):2745-2749.
8. Tehrani FR, Simbar M, Tohidi M, Hosseiniapanah F, Azizi F. The prevalence of polycystic ovary syndrome in a community sample of Iranian population: Iranian PCOS prevalence study. *Reprod Biol Endocrinol* 2011; 9(39):39.
9. Hughes C, Elgasim M, Layfield R, Atiomo W. Genomic and post-genomic approaches to polycystic ovary syndrome—progress so far: mini review. *Human Reproduction* 2006; 21(11):2766-2775.
10. Zhao Y, Fu L, Li R, Wang L-N, Yang Y, Liu N-N, et al. Metabolic profiles characterizing different phenotypes of polycystic ovary syndrome: plasma metabolomics analysis. *BMC medicine* 2012; 10(1):1.
11. Oliveira RdS Md, Redorat RG, Ziehe GH, Mansur VA, Conceição FL. Arterial hypertension and metabolic profile in patients with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Revista Brasileira de Ginecologia e Obstetrícia* 2013; 35(1):21-26.
12. Mukherjee S, Maitra A. Molecular & genetic factors contributing to insulin resistance in polycystic ovary syndrome. *Indian Journal of Medical Research* 2010; 131(6).
13. Diamanti-Kandarakis E. Polycystic ovarian syndrome: pathophysiology, molecular aspects and clinical implications. *Expert Reviews in molecular medicine* 2008; 10:e3.
14. Ehrmann DA. Polycystic ovary syndrome. *New England Journal of Medicine* 2005; 352(12):1223-1236.
15. Vrbikova J, Vondra K, Cibula D, Dvořáková K, Stanicka S, Šrámková D, et al. Metabolic syndrome in young Czech women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Human Reproduction* 2005; 20(12):3328-3332.
16. Essah PA, Nestler JE. Metabolic syndrome in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Fertility and sterility* 2006; 86: S18-S19.
17. Cheung L, Ma R, Lam P, Lok I, Haines C, So W, et al. Cardiovascular risks and metabolic syndrome in Hong Kong Chinese women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Human reproduction* 2008; 23(6):1431-1438.

18. Soares EMM, Azevedo GD, Gadelha RGN, Lemos TMAM, Maranhão TMO. Prevalence of the metabolic syndrome and its components in Brazilian women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Fertility and sterility* 2008; 89(3):649-655.
19. Dunaif A. Insulin resistance and the polycystic ovary syndrome: Mechanism and implications for pathogenesis. *Endocr Rev* 1997;18:774-800.
20. Korhonen S, Hippelainen M, Niskanen L, Vanhala M, Saarikoski S. Relationship of the metabolic syndrome and obesity to polycystic ovary syndrome; a controlled, population-based study. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2001;184:289-96.
21. Hosseinpanah F, Barzin M, Tehrani FR, Azizi F. The lack of association between polycystic ovary syndrome and metabolic syndrome: Iranian PCOS prevalence study. *Clin Endocrinol (Oxf)*. 2011; 75(5): 692-697.
22. Lankarani M, Valizadeh N, Heshmat R, Peimani M, Sohrabvand F. Evaluation of insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome in patients with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Gynecol Endocrinol*. 2009; 25(8): 504-507.
23. Rahmanpour H, Jamal L, Mousavinasab SN, Esmailzadeh A, Azarkhish K. Association between polycystic ovarian syndrome, overweight, and metabolic syndrome in adolescents. *J Pediatr Adolesc Gynecol*. 2012; 25(3): 208-212
24. Carmina E, Napoli N, Longo RA, Rini GB, Lobo RA. Metabolic syndrome in polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS): lower prevalence in southern Italy than in the USA and the influence of criteria for the diagnosis of PCOS. *Eur J of Endocrinol* 2006; 154(1): 141-145.
25. Pekhlivanov B, Kaleva-Khodzheva N, Orbetsova M, Mitkov M. Metabolic syndrome in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Akush Ginekol (Sofia)*. 2007;46(9):37-40.
26. Cheung LP, Ma RC, Lam PM, Lok IH, Haines CJ, So WY, Tong PC, Cockram CS, Chow CC, Goggins WB. Cardiovascular risks and metabolic syndrome in Hong Kong Chinese women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Hum Reprod*. 2008 Jun;23(6):1431-8.
27. Ehrmann DA, Liljenquist DR, Kasza K, Azziz R, et al. Prevalence and Predictors of the Metabolic Syndrome in Women with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome. *J Clin Endocrinol Metabol* 2006; 91(1): 48-53.
28. Soares EM, Azevedo GD, Gadelha RG, Lemos TM, Maranhão TM. Prevalence of the metabolic syndrome and its components in Brazilian women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Fertil Steril*. 2008 Mar;89(3):649-55.
29. Mehrabian F, Khani B, Kelishadi R, Kermani N. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance according to the phenotypic subgroups of polycystic ovary syndrome in a representative sample of Iranian females. *J Res Med Sci*. 2011; 16(6): 763-769.
30. Moini A, Javanmard F, Eslami B, Aletaha N. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome in polycystic ovarian syndrome women in a hospital of Tehran. *Iran J Reprod Med*. 2012; 10(2): 127-130.
31. Ziba Zahiri, Seyede Hajar Sharami, Forozan Milani, Fereshteh Mohammadi, Ehsan Kazemnejad, Hannan Ebrahimi, Seyede Fatemeh Dalil Heirati. Metabolic Syndrome in Patients with Polycystic Ovary Syndrome in Iran. *Int J Fertil Steril*. 2016 Jan-Mar; 9(4): 490-496.
32. Ruderman N, Schulman G. The Metabolic Syndrome. In: Jameson D. *Endocrinology* 5th ed. Churchill and Livingstone; 2006: 1158.
33. Holte J, Bergh C, Little H. Serum lipoprotein lipid profile in women with the polycystic ovary syndrome: relation to anthropometric, endocrine and metabolic variables. *clinical endocrinology(oxford)*. 1994.41:463-471.